

COLEGIO DE SAN ILDEFONSO

**ART BRUT
OUTSIDER ART
1ST INTERNATIONAL
MEETING IN
MEXICO CITY 2023**

TUESDAY, OCTOBER 10 – SATURDAY, OCTOBER 14, 2023

GOBIERNO DE ESPAÑA

MINISTERIO DE ASUNTOS EXTERIORES Y DE COOPERACIÓN

Cooperación Española

CCEMx

Centro Cultural de España en México

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CULTURA
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GOBIERNO DE LA CIUDAD DE MÉXICO

SECRETARÍA DE CULTURA

COLEGIO DE SAN ILDEFONSO

Coordinators:

Velebita Koričančić and Marianna Palerm Artís

PROGRAM

- **DOCUMENTARY FILMS | 5:00 - 6:30 pm**
GOYA CINEMA HALL | FREE ADMISSION

Tuesday, October 10
Moacir Arte Bruto
Brazil | 2006 | 71 min.
Dir. Walter Carvalho

Wednesday, October 11
In the Realms of the Unreal
USA | 2004 | 81 min.
Dir. Jessica Yu

Thursday, October 12
Marwencol
USA | 2010 | 83 min
Dir. Jeff Malmberg

Friday, October 12
What's Under Your Hat?
Spain | 2006 | 75 min
Dir. Lola Barrera, Iñaki Peñafiel

- **COURSE | THURSDAY, OCTOBER 12 AND FRIDAY, OCTOBER 13**
4:00 - 7:00 pm

***Approach to Art Brut as a School
of Unlearning: Creative Drive and
Search for Meaning***

Course Led by: Graciela García
José Clemente Orozco Hall
Prior registration | Limited capacity

Session 1

- Introduction: Creating from Within
- A Journey through Art Brut as Inspiration for Unlearning
- Drawing and Message I. Channeling Practice
- Group Practice

Session 2

- Creative Drive and Search for Meaning
- Sibyls in Art Brut. Reconnecting with the Earth
- Drawing and Message II. Channeling Practice

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• **PANELS | SATURDAY, OCTOBER 14 | (HYBRID FORMAT)**

The times correspond to the time zone of Mexico City

Broadcasting on the Colegio de San Ildefonso's channel: YouTube

Registry | 08:30 - 09:00

Break | 13:30 - 15:00

PANEL 1 | 09:00 - 11:00

Graciela García (Spain; independent researcher and representative for the Galerie Christian Berst and the Foundation Art Brut Project): *Unveiling the World: Cartography and Landscape in the Works of Andrés Fernández and Santiago Talavera*

Thomas Röske (Germany; President of the European Outsider Art Association and Director of the Prinzhorn Collection, Heidelberg): *The Prinzhorn Collection in Heidelberg, Germany - Past and Present*

Jelena Martinovic (Switzerland; Prof. & Head of Institute of Research in Fine Arts (IRAV), EDHEA - The Valais School of Art, HES-SO Valais-Wallis): *When art brut went chemical, c. 1920-1970s*

Ricardo Caballero (Mexico; visual artist and independent researcher): *Artistic practices for non-legally accountable populations in two prisons in Mexico City*

Panel Moderator: **Daniella Blejer** (México), independent researcher

PANEL 2 | 11:30 - 13:30

Solange de Oliveira (Federal University of Southern Bahia and Curator of the permanent exhibition *Arthur Bispo and his rosary*, at the Museu da Gente Sergipana, Brazil): *Arthur Bispo do Rosario and the Re-invention of Freedom*

Joana Masó (University of Barcelona): *Jean Dubuffet y François Tosquelles. The Art Brut that never came from Saint-Alban*

Daniela Bilopavlović Bedenik (Croatia; Senior Curator and Head of the Outsider Art Collection at the Museum of Contemporary Art in Zagreb): *Outsider Art in Croatia*

Amalija Stojsavljević (Serbia; Curator and Vice-President of the Association Art Brut Serbia): *Art Brut in the Balkans: Case study- Association Art Brut Serbia from Belgrade*

Panel Moderator: **María de la Concepción González Esteva** (México), independent researcher

PANEL 3 | 15:00 - 17:00

Leisa Rundquist (University of North Carolina, Asheville, USA, Co-Curator of series *Henry Darger: The Room Revealed*, at Intuit: The Center for Intuitive and Outsider Art, Chicago): *Approaching Gender Fluidity in Henry Darger's Art*

María Elena Lucero (National University of Rosario, Argentine): *Fragile Bodies: Convergences between Artistic practices, Psyche and Affectivities*

José Emmanuel Méndez Sánchez (National Autonomous University of Mexico): *"The brutes": A view on the Latin American marginal aesthetics*

Lorella Di Gregorio (University of Miami, USA): *Primitive, Folk, and Outsider: Debating Exvotos Definitions*

Panel Moderator: **Gabrielle Ramos García** (National Autonomous University of Mexico)

PANEL 4 | 17:30 - 19:30

Velebita Koričančić (Anáhuac University México/ National Autonomous University of Mexico): *Corporeal Surplus: Representations of the body in Latin American Outsider Art*

Paola Zavala (University Cultural Center Tlatelolco): *Who supports the neighborhood? - University Cultural Center Tlatelolco's Peace Laboratories*

Gabriela Borges Abraços (Adventist University of São Paulo, Brazil): *Art and affection: Mário Pedrosa and art workshops for the mentally ill*

Ana Karen G. Barajas (University of Hong-Kong, China): *Outsider art as an analysis tool in artistic work for persons with autism and schizophrenia*

Panel Moderator: **Ainhoa Vásquez Mejías** (National Autonomous University of Mexico)

Information and registrations
55 3602 0028 | acsiedu@gmail.com

All activities are open to the general public and free of charge | Limited capacity

